

Direction sensitive deformation measurement with epoxy/CNT nanocomposites

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SUMMARY

Electrically conductive polymer nanocomposites have potential for health monitoring and strain-sensing in structural polymer components. In this work CNT/epoxy-based material for direction sensitive strain sensing beams is produced in a simple process. The material is characterised and beams are tested in a 3-point bending setup where they exhibit a positive and negative gauge factor.

Keywords: nanocomposites, strain sensing, CNT, epoxy, piezoresistivity

INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles can be used for the introduction of functional properties into polymer matrix systems. In epoxy matrix systems low percolation thresholds can be achieved, especially with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [1,2]. Different dispersion techniques as well as curing conditions have influence on the formation of an electrically conductive network. Consequently material properties can vary and a gradient of electrical conductivity can be established in a large sample. If a mechanical load is applied to such a sample, the resulting changes in the conductive network structure will be reflected in a change of the overall sample resistance.

MATERIALS AND PREPARATION

In this work the matrix consisted of Huntsman, Araldite LY 556, an anhydride hardener Aradur 917 and the imidazole accelerator DY 070. The particles were multiwall carbon nanotubes of the type Graphistrength C 100 produced by Arkema.

The particles were dispersed into the highly viscous LY 556 resin using the three roll mill 120E produced by Exakt. In the three roll mill shear forces are induced by the different rotational speeds of the neighboring rolls. Exfoliation of the particles from the initially dense cluster is attained principally through shear forces, which move agglomerates and their primary particles relative to each other. Clusters are broken up by a stepless increase in shear rate as they enter the gap between the rolls. Because of this, shortening of nanotubes is expected to be less frequent than in e.g. ball milling

processes, especially for thorough dispersions. Residual agglomerates a few microns in size can be found even after prolonged dispersion. However, the material passed through gaps with a width of 5 μm several times, where the mixture was subjected to a shear rate in excess of $1.4 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$. and the amount of densely agglomerated particles is negligible.

The nanocomposite-resin was subsequently mixed with the low viscosity anhydride hardener and accelerator in a ratio of 100 : 90 : 1 parts by weight, respectively. The resulting mixture then contained 0.1 wt. % MWCNTs and was electrically conductive. The mixture was then cast into a thick walled, open topped aluminum mold. One mold was cured in a panel heated oven, while another was cured in a wall heated oven. The curing cycle was set to 4 h at 80 °C and 8 h at 140 °C.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the material processing and the sample in the three point bending experiment. The sample orientations denoted with “a”, “b” and “c” show the different ways the samples were tested in the bending beam setup.

Samples

Panels of approximately 150 x 100 x 7 mm were produced. Additionally double layer samples were produced by using only half the amount of nanocomposite and adding a layer of neat epoxy on top. The samples were cut out of the panel and contacted with silver paint and leads as indicated in the top right of Fig. 1. The double layer samples were produced with the interface of neat epoxy and nanocomposite aligned on the neutral fibre of the beam.

In another set of experiments samples for uniaxial tension tests were produced to determine the conductivity change with elongational strain. Furthermore references were produced to ascertain that the change of mechanical properties between neat epoxy and nanocomposite is negligible in this context.

Material Characterisation

A detailed characterization of the sample material was conducted. This was done to support the hypothesis, that the production process directly influences the observed

behavior. The general principle of electrical conduction through particles embedded in a non conducting matrix is described in [3-8]. A layer by layer analysis of the material showed that the conductivity distribution is indeed dependent on the production process. Raster sampling showed a pronounced influence of the proximity of boundaries, such as the mold walls, that reduce material flow or act as heat sources or sinks during curing. Furthermore, curing was done in two different ovens, which were nominally following the same temperature program. Due to the high heat of reaction the time delay in the temperature control loop of the oven has significant consequences on material behavior. A panel heated oven with a relatively close temperature control and a wall heated oven with the temperature sensor somewhat removed from the mold was used. It has become clear that the curing process can also influence the conductive network formed in a bulk sample significantly, e.g. through convection or variations in viscosity [9]. A characterisation of the nanocomposites macroscopic morphology was conducted by light microscopy.

Fig. 2: Optical micrograph of an area with relatively fine network structure of carbon nanotubes typical of the relatively highly conducting samples.

Fig. 3: Optical micrograph of an area with a coarse network structure of carbon nanotubes predominant in samples with low conductivity.

Fig. 4: Optical micrograph of an area with a coarse network structure irregular distribution of carbon nanotubes found mostly in the samples with coarse network structure.

One half of a produced panel was characterized regarding its electrical conductivity. Due to symmetry it is assumed that it is representative of the other half out of which bending beams were produced. The results of the characterisation can be attributed to the different areas of a bending beam as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Illustration of the areas used for characterisation of the sample material and their position in a bending beam sample.

It was cut into three height layers, which in turn were cut into tiles of approximately 10 x 10 x 1 mm. These were contacted with conductive silver paste on their large face. In this way it was possible to characterize the electrical conductivity with regard to height or distance from the side walls of the mold. The results for the conductivity distribution types of oven can be seen in Figure 6.

Fig. 6a: Average electrical conductivity at different height levels of the nanocomposite material cured in the panel heated oven. Fig. 6b: Average electrical conductivity at different height levels of the nanocomposite cured in the wall heated oven.

The electrical conductivity within one height level was also found to encompass a significant range. Between the different kinds of ovens a qualitative difference was visible an example of which is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7a: The area of a black circle is proportional to the relative conductivity of one $10 \times 10 \times 1$ mm sample in the high layer of a sample produced in the panel heated oven. Fig. 7b: The area of a black circle is proportional to the relative conductivity of one $10 \times 10 \times 1$ mm sample in the high layer of a sample produced in the wall heated oven.

It is obvious that the conductivity is generally higher at locations close to boundaries, which can be seen in both types of samples. The sample cured in the panel heated oven shows a quite systematic and symmetrical distribution, whereas only has high conductivity in the corners and some seemingly random variation across the rest of the area. It seems that local variations have characteristic sizes which allow them to be detected even with the coarse resolution of the sampling raster.

PIEZORESISTIVE CHARACTERISATION

Uniaxial tension test

In order to characterise the piezoresistive behavior under strain a relatively simple loading case was chosen. The sample was contacted in order to measure the change of narrow parallel region while the sample was deformed. The result can be seen in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Relative change of resistance with strain for a nanocomposite under tensile strain.

Double layer bending beam tests

In a bending beam tension and compression, as well as small amounts of shear are present. The actual strain occurring in the specimen is a function of the distance from the plane of zero stress and may exhibit values between zero and the strain of the outer fibre. The total resistance change measured can therefore be regarded as the summary resistance which depends on the local strain values. Therefore double layer samples were used to distinguish between these influences.

Samples bent in the orientation "a" shown in Fig. 1 show only the tensile strain in the change of their resistance as the compressed side consists of non conductive neat epoxy. Consequently sample bent in the "b" orientation show only the compressive strain influence. The experiments are reproducible and reversible in low strain regimes.

Fig. 9a): Relationship between strain of the outer fibre and the resistance change for three samples bent in the orientation “a”, with a tensile strain on the nanocomposite. Fig 9b): Relationship between strain of the outer fibre and the resistance change for three samples bent in the orientation “b”, with a compressive strain on the nanocomposite.

The slightly different behavior between the orientations can be attributed to the stress concentrations at the sample support.

Single layer bending beam tests

The loading cases “a” and “b” result in the same qualitative behaviour for single layer and double layer samples as can be seen in Fig. XXX. The main difference is the higher sensitivity exhibited by the double layer samples. The observed effect is essentially reversible. A more detailed description of the causes and nature of the conductivity changes can be found in [10] A vertical orientation of the highly conducting layer resulted in a significantly reduced sensitivity.

Fig. 10: Relationship between strain of the outer fibre and the resistance change for different loading cases in a single layer beam: a – highly conducting side under tensile strain, b – highly conducting side under compressive strain, c – highly conducting side parallel to load direction

CONCLUSIONS

In this work a simple process for the production of directional sensitive nanocomposite strain sensors was presented. The sensors show an approximately linear and reversible change of electrical resistance when subjected to elastic deformation. It was shown that a conductivity gradient/distribution can be induced through various parameters in the production process. The applicability of conductive nanocomposite epoxy matrix systems for stress/strain and damage sensing in FRP laminate structures has been shown already [11-13] and the ability to produce sensors with a directional sensitivity with a straightforward one-step processing route opens up a further possibility of application for this new class of functional polymers.

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